

TREATMENT TACTICS FOR COMPLEX CHOLEDOCHOLITHIASIS AND CALCULAR CHOLECYSTITIS

Author: Thankamoni Sindhu Sony¹

Coordinator: Moskal Vuk Oleksandr Petrovych¹

Affiliations:

¹ Bukovinian state medical university

Introduction

The number of cases of gallstone disease is constantly increasing, which is associated with changes in nutrition, sedentary lifestyle and aging of the population. Tens of thousands of cholecystectomies (removal of the gallbladder) are performed in Ukraine annually, which confirms the high level of clinical significance of this pathology. Gallstone disease is an urgent medical problem that requires attention from doctors, patients and health care systems both in Ukraine and in the world. Treatment of a combination of complex choledocholithiasis and calculous cholecystitis remains one of the most controversial topics in abdominal surgery, especially in cases where anatomical features or concomitant pathologies limit the use of minimally invasive techniques. The article studies the problem of choosing the optimal treatment tactics in the combination of complex choledocholithiasis and calculous cholecystitis, which remains an urgent challenge in modern surgery. The effectiveness and safety of various surgical approaches to treatment tactics in complex choledocholithiasis and calculous cholecystitis are analyzed.

Case Presentation

Based on the presentation of a clinical case, the results of patient treatment are analyzed. At the first stage, ERCP for lithoextraction was used, at the second stage, classical open cholecystectomy. The success rates of decompression, the frequency of postoperative complications and the duration of rehabilitation were evaluated.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that the preliminary performance of ERCP allows for effective sanitation of the common bile duct in 92-95% of cases and the elimination of mechanical jaundice, which minimizes the risks when performing the open stage of the operation. The choice of open cholecystectomy was due to the impossibility of endoscopic safe complete removal of stones from the common bile duct and the need for choledocholithotomy. This approach allowed to avoid serious intraoperative complications from the main vessels and bile ducts.

Keywords

Keywords: complex choledocholithiasis, calculous cholecystitis, ERCP, open cholecystectomy, mechanical jaundice.